
Apecosm Python package v1.1.0

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In the present document, the use of the Apecosm python package is described. The reading of Apecosm outputs as long as some computations (size-spectra, computation of mean length, diet matrix) are presented.

READING CONFIGURATION FILES

Apecosm configuration files can be read by using the `apecosm.read_config()` function. It reads the configuration file recursively. The program tries to convert the parameters into int, then into float. If both conversion fails, the parameter is kept as a string.

```
In [1]: config = apecosm.read_config(os.path.join('doc', 'data', 'config', 'oope.conf'))
```

```
In [2]: config.keys()
```

```
Out[2]: dict_keys(['simulation.restart.enabled', 'simulation.restart.lattice.file',  
↳ 'simulation.restart.file', 'biodiv.enabled', 'biodiv.nspecies', 'biodiv.maturity',  
↳ 'biodiv.maturity.beta', 'biodiv.mortality.predation', 'biodiv.mortality.predation.  
↳ exponent', 'biodiv.mortality.larva', 'biodiv.mortality.larva.exponent', 'biodiv.  
↳ mortality.ageing', 'biodiv.mortality.ageing.exponent', 'biodiv.mortality.disease',  
↳ mortality.natural', 'mortality.natural.exponent', 'biodiv.species.min', 'biodiv.  
↳ species.max', 'biology.taxa.eat_flagel', 'biology.taxa.eat_diatom', 'biology.taxa.eat_  
↳ microzoo', 'biology.taxa.eat_mesozoo', 'biology.taxa.eat_POC', 'biology.taxa.eat_GOC',  
↳ 'biology.ngroup', 'biology.group.names', 'biology.group.enabled', 'depth.max',  
↳ 'biology.trophic_interaction.file', 'biology.weight.nclass', 'biology.length.max',  
↳ 'biology.length.min', 'biology.weight.alpha', 'biology.weight.omega.min', 'biology.  
↳ weight.omega.incr', 'biology.deb.omega', 'biology.deb.eA', 'biology.deb.K', 'biology.  
↳ deb.MU', 'biology.deb.Eg', 'biology.deb.psi', 'biology.sexratio', 'biology.  
↳ reproduction.epsilon', 'biology.allometric.coeff', 'biology.fecundated_egg', 'biology.  
↳ schooling.slope', 'biology.schooling.crit', 'biology.mortality.disease', 'biology.  
↳ mortality.disease.dependence', 'biology.temperature.arrhenius', 'biology.temperature.  
↳ reference', 'biology.mortality.temperature', 'biology.selectivity.ratio.min', 'biology.  
↳ selectivity.ratio.max', 'biology.selectivity.gradient.min', 'biology.selectivity.  
↳ gradient.max', 'biology.selectivity.threshold', 'biology.functional_response.half_  
↳ saturation', 'biology.functional_response.half_saturation.dependence', 'movement.  
↳ diffusion.physical', 'movement.diffusion.biological', 'movement.swimming.max',  
↳ 'movement.advection.half_saturation', 'habitat.temperature_preference.enabled',  
↳ 'habitat.temperature_preference.sigma', 'habitat.temperature_limit.enabled', 'habitat.  
↳ temperature_limit.arrhenius', 'habitat.temperature_limit.min', 'habitat.temperature_  
↳ limit.max', 'habitat.oxygen.enabled', 'habitat.oxygen.threshold', 'habitat.oxygen.  
↳ response', 'habitat.light.enabled', 'habitat.light.same_day_night', 'habitat.light.  
↳ optimal', 'habitat.light.sigma', 'habitat.light.night_factor', 'predation.light.enabled  
↳ ', 'movement.vertical.advection', 'movement.vertical.diffusion', 'movement.vertical.  
↳ diffusivity', 'time.nsteps.growth', 'biomixing.enabled', 'biomixing.ethat', 'obc.  
↳ enabled', 'obc.west.enabled', 'obc.east.enabled', 'obc.north.enabled', 'obc.south.  
↳ enabled', 'obc.nudging_layer.thickness', 'obc.radiation.tau.in', 'obc.radiation.tau.out  
↳ ', 'forcing.poc.length.min', 'forcing.poc.length.max', 'forcing.goc.length.min',  
↳ 'forcing.goc.length.max', 'forcing.flagel.length.min', 'forcing.flagel.length.max',
```

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```

↪ 'forcing.diatom.length.min', 'forcing.diatom.length.max', 'forcing.microzoo.length.min
↪ ', 'forcing.microzoo.length.max', 'forcing.mesozoo.length.min', 'forcing.mesozoo.
↪ length.max', 'biology.schooling.crit.POC', 'biology.schooling.crit.GOC', 'biology.
↪ schooling.crit.diatom', 'biology.schooling.crit.flagel', 'biology.schooling.crit.
↪ microzoo', 'biology.schooling.crit.mesozoo', 'biology.schooling.slope.flagel',
↪ 'biology.schooling.slope.diatom', 'biology.schooling.slope.microzoo', 'biology.
↪ schooling.slope.mesozoo', 'biology.schooling.slope.POC', 'biology.schooling.slope.GOC',
↪ 'grid.type', 'grid.northfold.enabled', 'grid.nx', 'grid.i0', 'grid.ny', 'grid.j0',
↪ 'grid.nlevel.forcing', 'grid.nlevel', 'grid.periodicity.zonal.enabled', 'grid.
↪ periodicity.meridional.enabled', 'grid.depth.forcing.file', 'grid.depth.file', 'grid.
↪ mask.forcing.file', 'grid.mask.var.e1u', 'grid.mask.var.e1t', 'grid.mask.var.e1v',
↪ 'grid.mask.var.e2u', 'grid.mask.var.e2t', 'grid.mask.var.e2v', 'grid.mask.var.mask',
↪ 'grid.mask.var.masku', 'grid.mask.var.maskv', 'grid.mask.var.lon', 'grid.mask.var.lat',
↪ 'grid.mask.var.hdept', 'grid.mask.var.depth1d', 'grid.mask.var.e3t1d', 'grid.mask.var.
↪ e3t', 'grid.mask.var.e3u', 'grid.mask.var.e3v', 'mpi.regular.tiles', 'mpi.split.zonal',
↪ 'mpi.split.meridional', 'output.path', 'output.forcing.enabled', 'output.compression.
↪ level', 'output.constant.fields.enabled', 'output.restart.enabled', 'apecosm.save.freq
↪ ', 'output.nday_per_file', 'output.oope.enabled', 'output.current.enabled', 'output.
↪ oope3d.enabled', 'output.oope3d.nclass', 'output.oope3d.class', 'output.oope3d.class.
↪ file', 'output.mortality.enabled', 'output.growth.enabled', 'output.starvation.enabled
↪ ', 'output.functional_response.enabled', 'output.maturity.enabled', 'output.omega.
↪ enabled', 'output.natural_mortality.enabled', 'output.schooling.enabled', 'time.step',
↪ 'time.nsteps', 'restart.saving.frequency', 'restart.use.dayInit', 'time.spinup', 'time.
↪ year0', 'time.nsteps.movement', 'use.transport', 'forcing.var.diatom', 'forcing.var.
↪ microzoo', 'forcing.var.mesozoo', 'forcing.var.temperature', 'forcing.var.u', 'forcing.
↪ var.v', 'forcing.var.par', 'forcing.var.oxygen', 'forcing.var.flag', 'forcing.var.GOC',
↪ 'forcing.var.POC', 'forcing.file.prefix.goc', 'forcing.file.prefix.poc', 'forcing.
↪ file.prefix.diatom', 'forcing.file.prefix.microzoo', 'forcing.file.prefix.mesozoo',
↪ 'forcing.file.prefix.temperature', 'forcing.file.prefix.u', 'forcing.file.prefix.v',
↪ 'forcing.file.prefix.par', 'forcing.file.prefix.oxygen', 'forcing.file.prefix.flag',
↪ 'nemo.full.step', 'config.prefix', 'forcing.first.year', 'forcing.nstep.year', 'is.
↪ clim.diatom', 'is.clim.microzoo', 'is.clim.mesozoo', 'is.clim.temperature', 'is.clim.u
↪ ', 'is.clim.v', 'is.clim.par', 'is.clim.oxygen', 'is.clim.POC', 'is.clim.GOC',
↪ 'conversion.factor.diatom', 'conversion.offset.diatom', 'conversion.factor.microzoo',
↪ 'conversion.offset.microzoo', 'conversion.factor.mesozoo', 'conversion.offset.mesozoo',
↪ 'conversion.factor.GOC', 'conversion.offset.GOC', 'conversion.factor.POC',
↪ 'conversion.offset.POC', 'conversion.factor.temperature', 'conversion.offset.
↪ temperature', 'conversion.factor.u', 'conversion.offset.u', 'conversion.factor.v',
↪ 'conversion.offset.v', 'conversion.factor.oxygen', 'conversion.offset.oxygen',
↪ 'biology.dynamics.enabled'])

```

```
In [3]: config['grid.mask.var.e2v']
```

```
Out[3]: 'e2v'
```

OPENING DATA

In this section, functions that allow to open the NEMO/Pisces grid and data files and the Apecosm output files are described

2.1 Opening the mesh file

The NEMO/Pisces grid file is required to analyse Apecosm outputs, since it contains usefull variables such as longitudes and latitudes of the grid points, surface of the grid cells, land-sea mask, etc.

The mesh mask is opened by using the `apecosm.open_mesh_mask()` function:

```
In [1]: import os

In [2]: import apecosm

In [3]: mesh_file = os.path.join('doc', 'data', 'pacific_mesh_mask.nc')

In [4]: mesh = apecosm.open_mesh_mask(mesh_file)

In [5]: mesh
Out[5]:
<xarray.Dataset>
Dimensions:          (y: 108, x: 163, z: 75)
Dimensions without coordinates: y, x, z
Data variables: (12/44)
   e1f          (y, x) float64 ...
   e1t          (y, x) float64 ...
   e1u          (y, x) float64 ...
   e1v          (y, x) float64 ...
   e2f          (y, x) float64 ...
   e2t          (y, x) float64 ...
   ...          ...
   tmask        (z, y, x) int8 ...
   tmaskutil    (y, x) int8 ...
   umask        (z, y, x) int8 ...
   umaskutil    (y, x) int8 ...
   vmask        (z, y, x) int8 ...
   vmaskutil    (y, x) int8 ...
Attributes:
  file_name:    mesh_mask.nc
```

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```
TimeStamp: 08/11/2019 15:49:38 +0100
history:   Thu Aug 31 09:06:05 2023: ncks -4 -L 9 -d x,60,222 -d y,153,2...
NCO:      4.7.1
```

The `apecosm.open_mesh_mask()` opens the file and removes an eventual time dimension.

Dimension names can be replaced using the `replace_dims` argument, which is a dictionary with keys being the current dimension names and values being the new names:

```
mesh = apecosm.open_mesh_mask(mesh_file, replace_dims={'x': 'X', 'y': 'Y'})
mesh
```

Warning: Dimensions should be z, y and x

2.2 Opening the Apecosm constant file

Another import file is the Apecosm constant file, which contains biological constants (length, weight, etc.) that will be used to perform size-integration for instance.

It is opened by using the `apecosm.open_constants()` function:

```
In [6]: const = apecosm.open_constants(os.path.join('doc', 'data', 'apecosm/'))

In [7]: const
Out[7]:
<xarray.Dataset>
Dimensions:                (c: 5, w: 100, dn: 2, gprey: 5, wprey: 100)
Dimensions without coordinates: c, w, dn, gprey, wprey
Data variables: (12/13)
  weight                    (c, w) float64 dask.array<chunksize=(5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  length                   (c, w) float64 dask.array<chunksize=(5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  weight_step              (c, w) float64 dask.array<chunksize=(5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  weight_step2            (c, w) float64 dask.array<chunksize=(5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  length_step             (c, w) float64 dask.array<chunksize=(5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  troph_interaction        (dn, c, gprey) int8 dask.array<chunksize=(2, 5, 5), meta=np.
->ndarray>
  ...
  select_diatom           (c, w) float64 dask.array<chunksize=(5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  select_microzoo         (c, w) float64 dask.array<chunksize=(5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  select_mesozoo          (c, w) float64 dask.array<chunksize=(5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  select_poc               (c, w) float64 dask.array<chunksize=(5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  select_goc              (c, w) float64 dask.array<chunksize=(5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  select_flag             (c, w) float64 dask.array<chunksize=(5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
Attributes:
  Community_0: commu_1
  Community_1: commu_2
  Community_2: commu_3
  Community_3: commu_4
  Community_4: commu_5
```

The argument of this function is a **folder** that points to the location of the Apecosm outputs. This function also includes a `replace_dims` argument to eventually change the name of the dimensions.

Warning: Dimensions should be `c` (community), `w` (size-class), `y` and `x`

2.3 Opening the Apecosm data files

Apecosm data are opened using the `apecosm.open_apecosm_data()`.

```
In [8]: data = apecosm.open_apecosm_data(os.path.join('doc', 'data', 'apecosm'))

In [9]: data
Out[9]:
<xarray.Dataset>
Dimensions:                (time: 12, y: 108, x: 163, c: 5, w: 100,
                             community: 5, prey_group: 11)
Coordinates:
  * time                    (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 0...
Dimensions without coordinates: y, x, c, w, community, prey_group
Data variables:
  OOPE                      (time, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksi...
  ↪ 5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  community_diet_values     (time, y, x, community, w, prey_group) float32 dask.array
  ↪<chunksi...
  gamma1                    (time, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksi...
  ↪ 5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  mort_day                  (time, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksi...
  ↪ 5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  repfonct_day              (time, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksi...
  ↪ 5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
Attributes:
  history: Thu Aug 31 12:13:35 2023: ncks -O -4 -L 9 -d x,60,222 -d y,153,...
  NCO:      netCDF Operators version 5.0.6 (Homepage = http://nco.sf.net, C...
```

This function will read all the available outputs in the folder, except the constant file. In this example, the available outputs are:

- OOPE, i.e. biomass density.
- `community_diet_values`, i.e. diet matrix
- `gamma1`, i.e. the growth rate
- `mort_day`, i.e. the daily mortality rate
- `repfonct_day`, i.e. the functional response

To access one variable:

```
In [10]: data['OOPE']
Out[10]:
<xarray.DataArray 'OOPE' (time: 12, y: 108, x: 163, c: 5, w: 100)>
dask.array<open_dataset-OOPE, shape=(12, 108, 163, 5, 100), dtype=float32, chunksize=(12,
                                                                                               (continues on next page)
```

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```
→ 108, 163, 5, 100), chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Coordinates:
  * time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
Dimensions without coordinates: y, x, c, w
```

In order to facilitate the reading of multiple files, the arguments of the `xarray.open_mfdataset()` function can be used in the `open_apecosm_data()` one.

For instance in case of very heavy simulations (global simulations for instance), chunking options used to parallelize the processing can be provided as follows:

```
In [11]: data_chunked = apecosm.open_apecosm_data(os.path.join('doc', 'data', 'apecosm'),
.....:                                           chunks={'time': 1, 'x': 50, 'y': 50})
.....:
```

```
In [12]: data_chunked
```

```
Out[12]:
```

```
<xarray.Dataset>
Dimensions:                (time: 12, y: 108, x: 163, c: 5, w: 100,
                           community: 5, prey_group: 11)
Coordinates:
  * time                    (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 0...
Dimensions without coordinates: y, x, c, w, community, prey_group
Data variables:
  OOPE                     (time, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(1, 50, 50, 5,
→ 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  community_diet_values    (time, y, x, community, w, prey_group) float32 dask.array
→<chunksize=(1, 50, 50, 5, 100, 11), meta=np.ndarray>
  gamma1                   (time, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(1, 50, 50, 5,
→ 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  mort_day                 (time, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(1, 50, 50, 5,
→ 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  repfonct_day            (time, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(1, 50, 50, 5,
→ 100), meta=np.ndarray>
Attributes:
  history: Thu Aug 31 12:13:35 2023: ncks -O -4 -L 9 -d x,60,222 -d y,153,...
  NCO:     netCDF Operators version 5.0.6 (Homepage = http://nco.sf.net, C...
```

In this case, the chunk size is now $(1, 50, 50, 5, 100)$, while it was $(12, 108, 163, 5, 100)$ in the above.

Danger: The const, mesh and data objects must have the same dimension names. If it is not the case, use the `replace_dims` arguments to rename the dimensions. Dimension names are expected to be `time`, `y`, `x`, `c`, `w`.

2.4 Opening the NEMO/Pisces data files

The `apecosm.open_ltl_data()` function extracts NEMO/Pisces data files:

```
In [13]: ltl_data = apecosm.open_ltl_data(os.path.join('doc', 'data', 'pisces'),
.....:                                     replace_dims={'olevel': 'z'})
.....:

In [14]: ltl_data
Out[14]:
<xarray.Dataset>
Dimensions:                (time_counter: 12, z: 75, y: 108, x: 163, nvertex: 4,
                             axis_nbounds: 2)
Coordinates:
  nav_lat                  (y, x) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(108, 163), meta=np.
↪ ndarray>
  nav_lon                  (y, x) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(108, 163), meta=np.
↪ ndarray>
  * z                      (z) float32 0.5058 1.556 2.668 ... 5.698e+03 5.902e+03
  time_centered            (time_counter) object dask.array<chunksize=(12,), meta=np.
↪ ndarray>
  * time_counter           (time_counter) object 2018-01-16 12:00:00 ... 2018-...
Dimensions without coordinates: y, x, nvertex, axis_nbounds
Data variables: (12/16)
  GOC                      (time_counter, z, y, x) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(12, 75,
↪ 108, 163), meta=np.ndarray>
  O2                        (time_counter, z, y, x) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(12, 75,
↪ 108, 163), meta=np.ndarray>
  PHY                       (time_counter, z, y, x) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(12, 75,
↪ 108, 163), meta=np.ndarray>
  PHY2                      (time_counter, z, y, x) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(12, 75,
↪ 108, 163), meta=np.ndarray>
  POC                       (time_counter, z, y, x) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(12, 75,
↪ 108, 163), meta=np.ndarray>
  ZOO                       (time_counter, z, y, x) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(12, 75,
↪ 108, 163), meta=np.ndarray>
  ...
  time_centered_bounds      (time_counter, axis_nbounds) object dask.array<chunksize=(12,
↪ 2), meta=np.ndarray>
  time_counter_bounds       (time_counter, axis_nbounds) object dask.array<chunksize=(12,
↪ 2), meta=np.ndarray>
  PAR                       (time_counter, z, y, x) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(12, 75,
↪ 108, 163), meta=np.ndarray>
  e3t                       (time_counter, z, y, x) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(12, 75,
↪ 108, 163), meta=np.ndarray>
  so                        (time_counter, z, y, x) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(12, 75,
↪ 108, 163), meta=np.ndarray>
  thetao                    (time_counter, z, y, x) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(12, 75,
↪ 108, 163), meta=np.ndarray>
Attributes:
  name:                      GCB-eORCA1-JRA14-CO2ANTH_1m_ptrc_T
  description:                pisces sms variables
  title:                      pisces sms variables
```

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```
Conventions:          CF-1.6
timeStamp:           2019-Oct-28 05:38:48 GMT
uuid:                f0ec7b5f-db44-4aa8-b4c2-490c7c735040
LongName:            ORCA1_LIM3_PISCES NEMO configuration
history:             Wed May  3 14:48:47 2023: ncks -4 -L 9 -d x,60...
NCO:                 4.7.1
nco_openmp_thread_number: 1
```

The `replace_dims` arguments allows to replace dimension names, in order to make the name consistent with the dimensions in the mesh file. In this case, the `olevel` variable is replaced by `z`.

As for `open_apecosm_data()`, arguments of the `xarray.open_mfdataset()` function can be included in the `apecosm.open_ltl_data()` one.

Danger: Dimension names are expected to be <code>z, y, x</code> .
--

DATA EXTRACTION

3.1 Spatial average of Apecosm outputs

Apecosm outputs can be extracted over a given geographical by using the `apecosm.extract_oope_data()` function.

This function returns:

$$X_{mean}(t, c, w) = \frac{\int_{(y,x) \in S} X(t, y, x, c, w) \times dS(y, x)}{\int_{(y,x) \in S} dS(y, x)} \quad (3.1)$$

with S the domain where data are extracted, and dS the surface of the (i, j) cell, c is the community and w is the size-class. It is called as follows:

```
In [1]: spatial_mean = apecosm.extract_oope_data(data['OOPE'], mesh)
```

```
In [2]: spatial_mean
```

```
Out[2]:
```

```
<xarray.DataArray 'OOPE' (time: 12, c: 5, w: 100)>
dask.array<truediv, shape=(12, 5, 100), dtype=float64, chunksize=(12, 5, 100),
↳chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Coordinates:
  * time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
Dimensions without coordinates: c, w
Attributes:
  horizontal_norm_weight: <xarray.DataArray ()>\narray(1.06628289e+14)
```

with the first argument being the DataArray from which we extract the mean and the second argument being the mesh object (obtained with the `apecosm.open_mesh_mask()` function).

In order to extract the integral instead of the mean, the `apecosm.spatial_mean_to_integral()` function need to be called. This function multiply the above calculation by the denominator of (3.1), which is stored as the `horizontal_norm_weight` attribute

```
In [3]: spatial_integral = apecosm.spatial_mean_to_integral(spatial_mean)
```

```
In [4]: spatial_integral
```

```
Out[4]:
```

```
<xarray.DataArray (time: 12, c: 5, w: 100)>
dask.array<mul, shape=(12, 5, 100), dtype=float64, chunksize=(12, 5, 100),
↳chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Coordinates:
```

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```
* time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
Dimensions without coordinates: c, w
```

In addition, there is the possibility to provide a regional mask in order to extract the data over a given region. For instance, if we have a file containing different domains masks:

```
In [5]: domain_ds = xr.open_dataset(os.path.join('doc', 'data', 'domains.nc'))
```

```
In [6]: domain_ds
```

```
Out[6]:
```

```
<xarray.Dataset>
Dimensions:  (y: 108, x: 163)
Dimensions without coordinates: y, x
Data variables:
  domain_1  (y, x) float64 ...
  domain_3  (y, x) float64 ...
  domain_2  (y, x) float64 ...
```

We can extract the mean biomass over this domain as follows:

```
In [7]: regional_spatial_mean = apecosm.extract_oope_data(data['OOPE'], mesh, domain_ds[
↳ 'domain_1'])
```

```
In [8]: regional_spatial_mean
```

```
Out[8]:
```

```
<xarray.DataArray 'OOPE' (time: 12, c: 5, w: 100)>
dask.array<truediv, shape=(12, 5, 100), dtype=float64, chunksize=(12, 5, 100),
↳ chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Coordinates:
  * time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
Dimensions without coordinates: c, w
Attributes:
  horizontal_norm_weight:  <xarray.DataArray ()>\narray(1.22814443e+13)
```


Fig. 3.1: Example of a spatial domain

3.2 Spatial average of NEMO/Pisces outputs

The extraction of 3D biogeochemical forcing data is achieved by applying the following formula:

$$X_{mean}(t) = \frac{\int_{(y,x) \in S} \left[\sum_{z=z_{min}}^{z_{max}} X(t, z, y, x) dZ(z) \right] \times dS(y, x)}{\int_{(y,x) \in S} dS(y, x)} \quad (3.2)$$

It is achieved by using the `apecosm.extract_ltl_data()` function:

```
In [9]: spatial_mean_phy2 = apecosm.extract_ltl_data(ltl_data['PHY2'], mesh)

In [10]: spatial_mean_phy2
Out[10]:
<xarray.DataArray 'PHY2' (time_counter: 12)>
dask.array<truediv, shape=(12,), dtype=float64, chunksize=(12,), chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Coordinates:
  time_centered  (time_counter) object dask.array<chunksize=(12,), meta=np.ndarray>
 * time_counter  (time_counter) object 2018-01-16 12:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 1...
Attributes:
  horizontal_norm_weight:  106628289264625.23
```

This function will first vertically **integrate** the LTL biomass (converting from *mmol/m3* into *mmol/m2*, term in brackets in (3.2)). Then the horizontal **average** is computed. This choice has been made to be consistent with Apecosm outputs. Indeed, OOPE is provided as a vertically integrated biomass. Therefore, vertical integration need to be performed on LTL outputs in order to draw the size-spectra.

However, it remains possible to convert the horizontal average into an horizontal integral as follows:

```
In [11]: spatial_integral_phy2 = apecosm.spatial_mean_to_integral(spatial_mean_phy2)

In [12]: spatial_integral_phy2
Out[12]:
<xarray.DataArray 'PHY2' (time_counter: 12)>
dask.array<mul, shape=(12,), dtype=float64, chunksize=(12,), chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Coordinates:
  time_centered  (time_counter) object dask.array<chunksize=(12,), meta=np.ndarray>
 * time_counter  (time_counter) object 2018-01-16 12:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 1...
```

There is also the possibility to control the depth at which the average is performed and the domain used for the averaging. For instance, to compute the average between 0 and 200m over the domain defined above:

```
In [13]: spatial_0_200_reg_mean_phy2 = apecosm.extract_ltl_data(ltl_data['PHY2'],
.....:                                                         mesh,
.....:                                                         mask_dom=domain_ds[
↪ 'domain_1'],
.....:                                                         depth_limits=[0, 200])
.....:

In [14]: spatial_0_200_reg_mean_phy2
Out[14]:
<xarray.DataArray 'PHY2' (time_counter: 12)>
dask.array<truediv, shape=(12,), dtype=float64, chunksize=(12,), chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Coordinates:
```

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Fig. 3.2: Mean concentration of PHY2

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```
time_centered (time_counter) object dask.array<chunksize=(12,), meta=np.ndarray>  
* time_counter (time_counter) object 2018-01-16 12:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 1...  
Attributes:  
horizontal_norm_weight: 12281444279203.426
```


Fig. 3.3: Mean concentration of PHY2 over the subregion and between 0 and 200m

CALCULATIONS

Using the different variables defined in [Section 3](#), there is different diagnostics available in the *Apecosm* python package.

4.1 Time averaging

There is the possibility to compute time averages. This is done by using the `apecosm.extract_time_means()` function, which allows to compute either full time average, yearly, seasonal or monthly averages.

4.1.1 Full time average

For the time-average over the entire simulation:

```
In [1]: data_temporal_mean = apecosm.extract_time_means(data)

In [2]: data_temporal_mean
Out[2]:
<xarray.Dataset>
Dimensions:                (y: 108, x: 163, c: 5, w: 100, community: 5,
                             prey_group: 11)
Dimensions without coordinates: y, x, c, w, community, prey_group
Data variables:
  OOPE                      (y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(108, 163, 5, 100),
  ↪meta=np.ndarray>
  community_diet_values      (y, x, community, w, prey_group) float32 dask.array
  ↪<chunksize=(108, 163, 5, 100, 11), meta=np.ndarray>
  gamma1                    (y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(108, 163, 5, 100),
  ↪meta=np.ndarray>
  mort_day                  (y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(108, 163, 5, 100),
  ↪meta=np.ndarray>
  repfonct_day              (y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(108, 163, 5, 100),
  ↪meta=np.ndarray>
```

with `data` the output of the `apecosm.open_apecosm_data()` function.

In this example, there is no time dimension anymore

4.1.2 Yearly average

To compute the yearly mean, the function must be called with a `year` argument:

```
In [3]: data_yearly_mean = apecosm.extract_time_means(data, 'year')

In [4]: data_yearly_mean
Out[4]:
<xarray.Dataset>
Dimensions:                (year: 1, y: 108, x: 163, c: 5, w: 100,
                             community: 5, prey_group: 11)
Coordinates:
  * year                    (year) int64 2018
Dimensions without coordinates: y, x, c, w, community, prey_group
Data variables:
  OOPE                      (year, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(1, 108, 163,
  ↪5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  community_diet_values     (year, y, x, community, w, prey_group) float32 dask.array
  ↪<chunksize=(1, 108, 163, 5, 100, 11), meta=np.ndarray>
  gammal                    (year, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(1, 108, 163,
  ↪5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  mort_day                  (year, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(1, 108, 163,
  ↪5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  repfonct_day              (year, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(1, 108, 163,
  ↪5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
Attributes:
  history: Thu Aug 31 12:13:35 2023: ncks -O -4 -L 9 -d x,60,222 -d y,153,...
  NCO:      netCDF Operators version 5.0.6 (Homepage = http://nco.sf.net, C...
```

In this case, the time dimension has been replaced by a `year` dimension, which contains only one element.

4.1.3 Seasonal average

To compute the seasonal mean, the function must be called with a `season` argument:

```
In [5]: data_yearly_mean = apecosm.extract_time_means(data, 'season')

In [6]: data_yearly_mean
Out[6]:
<xarray.Dataset>
Dimensions:                (season: 4, y: 108, x: 163, c: 5, w: 100,
                             community: 5, prey_group: 11)
Coordinates:
  * season                  (season) object 'DJF' 'JJA' 'MAM' 'SON'
Dimensions without coordinates: y, x, c, w, community, prey_group
Data variables:
  OOPE                      (season, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(1, 108,
  ↪163, 5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  community_diet_values     (season, y, x, community, w, prey_group) float32 dask.array
  ↪<chunksize=(1, 108, 163, 5, 100, 11), meta=np.ndarray>
  gammal                    (season, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(1, 108,
  ↪163, 5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  mort_day                  (season, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(1, 108,
  ↪163, 5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
```

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```

↪163, 5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  repfonct_day          (season, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(1, 108, 163,
↪163, 5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
Attributes:
  history: Thu Aug 31 12:13:35 2023: ncks -O -4 -L 9 -d x,60,222 -d y,153,...
  NCO:      netCDF Operators version 5.0.6 (Homepage = http://nco.sf.net, C...

```

In this case, the time dimension has been replaced by a *season* dimension, which contains 4 elements. Note that the user does not have the choice of the seasons, which are DJF, JJA MAM and SON

4.1.4 Monthly average

To compute the monthly mean, the function must be called with a `month` argument:

```

In [7]: data_yearly_mean = apecosm.extract_time_means(data, 'month')

In [8]: data_yearly_mean
Out[8]:
<xarray.Dataset>
Dimensions:                (month: 12, y: 108, x: 163, c: 5, w: 100,
                             community: 5, prey_group: 11)
Coordinates:
  * month                   (month) int64 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12
Dimensions without coordinates: y, x, c, w, community, prey_group
Data variables:
  OOPE                     (month, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(1, 108, 163,
↪ 5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  community_diet_values    (month, y, x, community, w, prey_group) float32 dask.array
↪<chunksize=(1, 108, 163, 5, 100, 11), meta=np.ndarray>
  gamma1                   (month, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(1, 108, 163,
↪ 5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  mort_day                 (month, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(1, 108, 163,
↪ 5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
  repfonct_day            (month, y, x, c, w) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(1, 108, 163,
↪ 5, 100), meta=np.ndarray>
Attributes:
  history: Thu Aug 31 12:13:35 2023: ncks -O -4 -L 9 -d x,60,222 -d y,153,...
  NCO:      netCDF Operators version 5.0.6 (Homepage = http://nco.sf.net, C...

```

In this case, the time dimension has been replaced by a *month* dimension, which contains 12 elements.

Warning: The computation of seasonal and monthly averages are available only when Apecosm outputs are provided with at least a monthly time step.

4.2 Size-integration

The `apecosm.extract_oope_size_integration()` integrates the biomass along the size-dimension.

$$B(t, y, x, c) = \sum_w OOPE(t, y, x, c, w) \times \Delta W(c, w)$$

```
In [1]: biomass_maps = apecosm.extract_oope_size_integration(data['OOPE'], const)

In [2]: biomass_maps
Out[2]:
<xarray.DataArray (time: 12, y: 108, x: 163, c: 5)>
dask.array<sum-aggregate, shape=(12, 108, 163, 5), dtype=float64, chunksize=(12, 108,
↪163, 5), chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Coordinates:
  * time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
Dimensions without coordinates: y, x, c
```

The function can also be called on spatially averaged or integrated biomass density, computed using the `apecosm.extract_oope_data()`:

$$B(t, c) = \sum_w OOPE(t, c, w) \times \Delta W(c, w)$$

```
In [3]: biomass_timeseries = apecosm.extract_oope_size_integration(spatial_mean, const)

In [4]: biomass_timeseries
Out[4]:
<xarray.DataArray (time: 12, c: 5)>
dask.array<sum-aggregate, shape=(12, 5), dtype=float64, chunksize=(12, 5),
↪chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Coordinates:
  * time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
Dimensions without coordinates: c
```

The biomass time-series can then be plotted as follows:

```
In [5]: comnames = apecosm.extract_community_names(const)

In [6]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))

In [7]: plt.subplots_adjust(hspace=0.4)

In [8]: for c in range(len(comnames)):
...:     ax = plt.subplot(3, 2, c + 1)
...:     biomass_timeseries.isel(c=c).plot()
...:     ax.set_title('Averaged biomass, c = %s' % comnames[c])
...:     ax.grid(True)
...:

In [9]: ax = plt.subplot(3, 2, 6)

In [10]: biomass_timeseries.sum(dim='c').plot()
```

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```
Out[10]: [<matplotlib.lines.Line2D at 0x7f0f23047970>]
```

```
In [11]: ax.set_title('Averaged biomass, tot.')
```

```
Out[11]: Text(0.5, 1.0, 'Averaged biomass, tot.')
```

```
In [12]: ax.grid(True)
```


Fig. 4.1: Averaged biomass

In this case, the integration is performed along all the size-classes. It is also possible to provide length boundaries (**in cm**), using the `lmin` and `lmax` dimensions. For biomass between 0 and 3cm :

```
In [13]: biomass_timeseries_0_3 = apecosm.extract_oope_size_integration(spatial_mean,
.....:                                                                    const, lmax=3)
.....:
```

```
In [14]: biomass_timeseries_0_3
```

```
Out[14]:
```

```
<xarray.DataArray (time: 12, c: 5)>
```

```
dask.array<sum-aggregate, shape=(12, 5), dtype=float64, chunksize=(12, 5),
```

```
↳ chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
```

```
Coordinates:
```

```
* time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
```

```
Dimensions without coordinates: c
```


Fig. 4.2: Averaged biomass between 0 and 3cm

For biomass between 3 and 20 cm

```
In [15]: mean_biomass_3_20 = apecosm.extract_oope_size_integration(spatial_mean,
.....:                                                             const, lmin=3,
↳lmax=20)
.....:

In [16]: mean_biomass_3_20
Out[16]:
<xarray.DataArray (time: 12, c: 5)>
dask.array<sum-aggregate, shape=(12, 5), dtype=float64, chunksize=(12, 5),
↳chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Coordinates:
  * time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
Dimensions without coordinates: c
```


Fig. 4.3: Integrated biomass between 3 and 20cm

For biomass greater than 20 cm:

```
In [17]: mean_biomass_20_inf = apecosm.extract_oope_size_integration(spatial_mean,
.....:                                                             const,
↳lmin=20)
.....:
```

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```
In [18]: mean_biomass_20_inf
Out[18]:
<xarray.DataArray (time: 12, c: 5)>
dask.array<sum-aggregate, shape=(12, 5), dtype=float64, chunksize=(12, 5),
↳ chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Coordinates:
  * time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
Dimensions without coordinates: c
```


Fig. 4.4: Integrated biomass > 20cm

Danger: Size-integration must only be applied to OOPE

4.3 Computation of mean length

The mean length of each community can be computed by using a weighted mean, in which the weight is provided by the biomass in each grid cell:

$$L_{mean}(t, c) = \frac{\sum_{y,x,w} OOPE(t, y, x, c, w) \times \Delta W(c, w) \times dS(x, y) \times L(c, w)}{\sum_{y,x,w} OOPE(t, y, x, c, w) \times \Delta W(c, w) \times dS(x, y)}$$

Since $L(c, w)$ does not depend on x and y , it can be rewritten as follows:

$$L_{mean}(t, c) = \frac{\sum_w L(c, w) \times \Delta W(c, w) \left[\sum_{y,x} OOPE(t, y, x, c, w) \times dS(x, y) \right]}{\sum_w \Delta W(c, w) \left[\sum_{y,x} OOPE(t, y, x, c, w) \times dS(x, y) \right]} \quad (4.1)$$

We notice that the values in brackets are the outputs of the successive calls of `apecosm.extract_oope_data()` and `apecosm.spatial_mean_to_integral()`. Therefore, the mean length over a given domain can be computed by first computing the spatial integral:

```
In [1]: spatial_mean = apecosm.extract_oope_data(data['OOPE'], mesh)

In [2]: spatial_integral = apecosm.spatial_mean_to_integral(spatial_mean)

In [3]: spatial_integral
Out[3]:
<xarray.DataArray (time: 12, c: 5, w: 100)>
dask.array<mul, shape=(12, 5, 100), dtype=float64, chunksize=(12, 5, 100),
↳ chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Coordinates:
  * time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
Dimensions without coordinates: c, w
```

When this is done, the integration of (4.1) is achieved by using the `apecosm.extract_mean_size()` function as follows:

```
In [4]: com_mean_length = apecosm.extract_mean_size(spatial_integral, const, 'length')

In [5]: com_mean_length
Out[5]:
<xarray.DataArray 'length' (c: 5, time: 12)>
dask.array<truediv, shape=(5, 12), dtype=float64, chunksize=(5, 12), chunktype=numpy.
↳ ndarray>
Coordinates:
  * time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
Dimensions without coordinates: c
```

Note that the `apecosm.extract_mean_size()` returns the mean for each community.

Finally, the mean length time-series can be plotted as follows:

```
In [6]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))

In [7]: plt.subplots_adjust(hspace=0.4)

In [8]: for c in range(5):
```

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```

.....: ax = plt.subplot(3, 2, c + 1)
.....: com_mean_length.isel(c=c).plot()
.....: ax.set_title('Mean length (m), c = %d' %c)
.....: ax.grid(True)
.....:

```


Fig. 4.5: Mean length

To compute the mean weight:

```
In [9]: com_mean_weight = apocosm.extract_mean_size(spatial_integral, const, 'weight')
```

```
In [10]: com_mean_weight
```

```
Out[10]:
```

```

<xarray.DataArray 'weight' (c: 5, time: 12)>
dask.array<truediv, shape=(5, 12), dtype=float64, chunksize=(5, 12), chunktype=numpy.
  ↳ ndarray>
Coordinates:
  * time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
Dimensions without coordinates: c

```

To compute the mean length or weight over a given basin, the argument must be the integral over this given region:

```
In [11]: com_reg_mean_length = apocosm.extract_mean_size(regional_spatial_integral,
↳ const, 'length')
```

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Fig. 4.6: Mean weight

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```
In [12]: com_reg_mean_length
Out[12]:
<xarray.DataArray 'length' (c: 5, time: 12)>
dask.array<truediv, shape=(5, 12), dtype=float64, chunksize=(5, 12), chunktype=numpy.
↳ndarray>
Coordinates:
  * time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
Dimensions without coordinates: c
```

```
In [13]: com_reg_mean_weight = apecosm.extract_mean_size(regional_spatial_integral,
↳const, 'weight')
```

```
In [14]: com_reg_mean_weight
Out[14]:
<xarray.DataArray 'weight' (c: 5, time: 12)>
dask.array<truediv, shape=(5, 12), dtype=float64, chunksize=(5, 12), chunktype=numpy.
↳ndarray>
Coordinates:
  * time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
Dimensions without coordinates: c
```

4.4 Cumulated biomass

The cumulated proportion of fish biomass can be computed by using the `compute_size_cumprop()` function. It returns:

$$B_{cum}(t, c, w_0) = \frac{\sum_{w=0}^{w_0} B(t, c, w) \times \Delta W(c, w)}{\sum_{w=0}^{w_{max}} B(t, c, w) \times \Delta W(c, w)}$$

This function is called as follows:

```
In [1]: com_cum_biom = apecosm.compute_size_cumprop(spatial_integral, const)
```

```
In [2]: com_cum_biom
Out[2]:
<xarray.DataArray (time: 12, c: 5, w: 100)>
dask.array<mul, shape=(12, 5, 100), dtype=float64, chunksize=(12, 5, 100),
↳chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Coordinates:
  * time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
Dimensions without coordinates: c, w
```

This function returns the cumulated biomass for each community.

Danger: It is not possible to obtain the cumulated biomass including all the community, since it supposes that all the communities have the same size-classes, which is not always the case. However, it may be possible to compute it manually.

We can now draw the cumulated biomass proportion averaged over the entire simulation period. First, we extract the temporal mean of the cumulated biomass.

```
In [3]: mean_com_cum_biom = apecosm.extract_time_means(com_cum_biom)
```

Now we can draw the cumulated biomass.

```
In [4]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
```

```
In [5]: plt.subplots_adjust(hspace=0.4)
```

```
In [6]: for c in range(5):
...:     ax = plt.subplot(3, 2, c + 1)
...:     plt.fill_between(const['length'].isel(c=c), 0, mean_com_cum_biom.isel(c=c),
↪ color='lightgray')
...:     plt.plot(const['length'].isel(c=c), mean_com_cum_biom.isel(c=c), color='black
↪ ')
...:     ax.set_title('Cumulated proportion, c = %d' %c)
...:     ax.set_ylabel('%')
...:     ax.set_ylim(0, 100)
...:     ax.set_xlim(const['length'].min(), const['length'].max())
...:     ax.set_xscale('log')
...:     ax.grid(True)
...: 
```


Fig. 4.7: Mean cumulated biomass

4.5 Size-spectra

4.5.1 Plotting of LTL size spectra

The size-spectra associated with a given LTL can be plotted using the `compute_spectra_ltl()` function.

First, the spatial mean is computed, as in [Section 3.2](#):

```
In [1]: depth_max = 1000

In [2]: ltl_phy2 = apecosm.extract_ltl_data(ltl_data['PHY2'], mesh, depth_limits=[None,
↳ depth_max])

In [3]: ltl_phy2
Out[3]:
<xarray.DataArray 'PHY2' (time_counter: 12)>
dask.array<truediv, shape=(12,), dtype=float64, chunksize=(12,), chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Coordinates:
  time_centered  (time_counter) object dask.array<chunksize=(12,), meta=np.ndarray>
  * time_counter  (time_counter) object 2018-01-16 12:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 1...
Attributes:
  horizontal_norm_weight: 106628289264625.23
```

And the time-mean is then computed:

```
In [4]: ltl_phy2_mean = apecosm.extract_time_means(ltl_phy2)

In [5]: ltl_phy2_mean
Out[5]:
<xarray.DataArray 'PHY2' ()>
array(28.78154957)
```

Then, the size-spectra is plotted as follows:

```
In [6]: fig = plt.figure()

In [7]: ax = plt.gca()

In [8]: L = [10e-6, 100e-6]

In [9]: apecosm.compute_spectra_ltl(ltl_phy2_mean, L, output_var='weight', label='PHY2')
Out[9]: <matplotlib.lines.Line2D at 0x7f0f28ae7cd0>

In [10]: ax.set_xscale('log')

In [11]: ax.set_yscale('log')

In [12]: ax.set_ylabel("Biomass")
Out[12]: Text(0, 0.5, 'Biomass')

In [13]: ax.set_xlabel('Weight (kg)')
Out[13]: Text(0.5, 0, 'Weight (kg)')
```

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```
In [14]: ax.set_title('PHY2 size-spectra')
Out[14]: Text(0.5, 1.0, 'PHY2 size-spectra')
```

The L variable is the lower and upper bound of the LTL length, as used in the Apecosm configuration (forcing .XXX.length.min and forcing .XXX.length.max parameters).

Fig. 4.8: Diatoms size-spectra as a function of weight

Note that the size-spectra can also be plotted as a function of length by setting the `output_var` argument to `length`.

```
In [15]: fig = plt.figure()
In [16]: ax = plt.gca()
In [17]: L = [10e-6, 100e-6]
In [18]: apecosm.compute_spectra_ltl(ltl_phy2_mean, L, output_var='length', label='PHY2')
Out[18]: <matplotlib.lines.Line2D at 0x7f0f22836bf0>
In [19]: ax.set_xscale('log')
In [20]: ax.set_yscale('log')
In [21]: ax.set_ylabel("Biomass")
```

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```

Out[21]: Text(0, 0.5, 'Biomass')
In [22]: ax.set_xlabel('Length (m)')
Out[22]: Text(0.5, 0, 'Length (m)')
In [23]: ax.set_title('PHY2 size-spectra')
Out[23]: Text(0.5, 1.0, 'PHY2 size-spectra')

```


Fig. 4.9: Diatoms size-spectra as a function of length

4.5.2 Plotting of Apecosm size spectra

Apecosm size-spectra is plotting using the `apecosm.plot_oope_spectra()` function.

First, we extract the Apecosm biomass on a given region region:

```

In [24]: ts = apecosm.extract_oope_data(data['OOPE'], mesh)
In [25]: ts
Out[25]:
<xarray.DataArray 'OOPE' (time: 12, c: 5, w: 100)>
dask.array<truediv, shape=(12, 5, 100), dtype=float64, chunksize=(12, 5, 100),
↳ chunktype=numpy.ndarray>

```

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Coordinates:

* time (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00

Dimensions without coordinates: c, w

Attributes:

horizontal_norm_weight: <xarray.DataArray ()>\narray(1.06628289e+14)

Then, we compute the time mean:

In [26]: `tsmean = apocosm.extract_time_means(ts)`

In [27]: `tsmean`

Out[27]:

<xarray.DataArray 'OOPE' (c: 5, w: 100)>

```
array([[1.30149325e+06, 2.55347049e+06, 3.77967286e+06, 4.45099087e+06,
        4.32907629e+06, 3.61570494e+06, 2.73209272e+06, 1.97408747e+06,
        1.41546203e+06, 1.02548778e+06, 7.56045400e+05, 5.67651459e+05,
        4.33508040e+05, 3.35940796e+05, 2.63521229e+05, 2.08757558e+05,
        1.66794133e+05, 1.34186211e+05, 1.08428582e+05, 8.79857332e+04,
        7.16195503e+04, 5.84193429e+04, 4.77146184e+04, 3.90054776e+04,
        3.19083195e+04, 2.61154324e+04, 2.13896845e+04, 1.75259576e+04,
        1.43641161e+04, 1.17300774e+04, 9.58886764e+03, 7.85181472e+03,
        6.44061190e+03, 5.28732343e+03, 4.34109406e+03, 3.43649114e+03,
        2.76531954e+03, 2.25270965e+03, 1.85285882e+03, 1.53576214e+03,
        1.28076672e+03, 1.07353370e+03, 9.03614958e+02, 7.63209549e+02,
        6.46445808e+02, 5.48250641e+02, 4.66092905e+02, 3.97039229e+02,
        3.38791926e+02, 2.89514491e+02, 2.47700727e+02, 2.12113329e+02,
        1.81729934e+02, 1.55710491e+02, 1.33363205e+02, 1.14124687e+02,
        9.75349010e+01, 8.32193161e+01, 7.08697775e+01, 6.02387573e+01,
        5.11074810e+01, 4.32860536e+01, 3.66056090e+01, 3.09124416e+01,
        2.60757887e+01, 2.19700012e+01, 1.84822793e+01, 1.55249709e+01,
        1.30096748e+01, 1.08629852e+01, 9.02154794e+00, 7.43870543e+00,
        6.06898773e+00, 4.87689489e+00, 3.83635154e+00, 2.91686205e+00,
        2.09706847e+00, 1.37391651e+00, 7.70417277e-01, 3.38936780e-01,
        ...
        1.55822760e+03, 1.29875731e+03, 1.07091350e+03, 8.68081868e+02,
        6.90454673e+02, 5.41591044e+02, 4.21601297e+02, 3.28442356e+02,
        2.62296666e+02, 2.16458004e+02, 1.84686783e+02, 1.61547116e+02,
        1.43543216e+02, 1.28719312e+02, 1.16046597e+02, 1.05005266e+02,
        9.53052533e+01, 8.67882883e+01, 7.94608041e+01, 7.31473947e+01,
        6.71914888e+01, 6.11681483e+01, 5.48563566e+01, 4.86436637e+01,
        4.28564778e+01, 3.76122245e+01, 3.29823395e+01, 2.89268659e+01,
        2.53781129e+01, 2.22702342e+01, 1.95464692e+01, 1.71709768e+01,
        1.51081945e+01, 1.33231693e+01, 1.17709560e+01, 1.04240502e+01,
        9.25328480e+00, 8.23533019e+00, 7.35199719e+00, 6.58014258e+00,
        5.90196868e+00, 5.29656496e+00, 4.74460468e+00, 4.23903531e+00,
        3.7728380e+00, 3.35945794e+00, 2.98308328e+00, 2.64667233e+00,
        2.34699733e+00, 2.07958498e+00, 1.84145321e+00, 1.62924666e+00,
        1.43935428e+00, 1.26962540e+00, 1.11734487e+00, 9.80880695e-01,
        8.58491508e-01, 7.48374374e-01, 6.49319716e-01, 5.59822917e-01,
        4.78855509e-01, 4.05361268e-01, 3.38754120e-01, 2.78668357e-01,
        2.24930868e-01, 1.77637846e-01, 1.36991889e-01, 1.02772831e-01,
        7.41671282e-02, 5.04930903e-02, 3.16649233e-02, 1.81723179e-02,
```

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```
1.00125915e-02, 5.25567298e-03, 2.18954445e-03, 6.56685982e-04,
1.50464756e-04, 2.42515050e-05, 2.48062160e-06, 1.45117865e-07]])
Dimensions without coordinates: c, w
```

The size-spectrum can now be plotted using the `apecosm.plot_oope_spectra()` function as follows:

```
In [28]: fig = plt.figure()

In [29]: ax = plt.gca()

In [30]: cs = apecosm.plot_oope_spectra(tsmean, const, output_var='weight')

In [31]: ax.set_xscale('log')

In [32]: ax.set_yscale('log')

In [33]: ax.set_ylim(1e-6, 1e8)
Out[33]: (1e-06, 100000000.0)

In [34]: ax.set_ylabel("Biomass")
Out[34]: Text(0, 0.5, 'Biomass')

In [35]: ax.set_xlabel('Weight (kg)')
Out[35]: Text(0.5, 0, 'Weight (kg)')

In [36]: ax.set_title('Apecosm size-spectra')
Out[36]: Text(0.5, 1.0, 'Apecosm size-spectra')

In [37]: plt.legend()
Out[37]: <matplotlib.legend.Legend at 0x7f0f2261efe0>
```

4.5.3 Size-spectra including LTL/HTL

In order to draw the size-spectra for all LTL variables and Apecosm outputs, we first need to extract all LTL variables over the same regions, as done for PHY2 in the above:

```
In [38]: ltl_zoo2 = apecosm.extract_ltl_data(ltl_data['Z002'], mesh, depth_limits=[None, ↵
↳depth_max]).compute()

In [39]: ltl_zoo = apecosm.extract_ltl_data(ltl_data['Z00'], mesh, depth_limits=[None, ↵
↳depth_max]).compute()

In [40]: ltl_goc = apecosm.extract_ltl_data(ltl_data['GOC'], mesh, depth_limits=[None, ↵
↳depth_max]).compute()

In [41]: ltl_goc_mean = ltl_goc.mean(dim='time_counter')

In [42]: ltl_zoo_mean = ltl_zoo.mean(dim='time_counter')

In [43]: ltl_zoo2_mean = ltl_zoo2.mean(dim='time_counter')
```


Fig. 4.10: Apecosm size-spectra as a function of weight

When this is done, we call all the `apecosm.plot_oope_spectra()` and the `apecosm.compute_spectra_ltl()` functions on the same axis:

```
In [44]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(10, 8))

In [45]: ax = plt.gca()

In [46]: cs = apecosm.plot_oope_spectra(tsmean, const, output_var='weight')

In [47]: L = [10e-6, 100e-6]

In [48]: apecosm.compute_spectra_ltl(ltl_phy2_mean, L, output_var='weight', label='PHY2')
Out[48]: <matplotlib.lines.Line2D at 0x7f0f226e75b0>

In [49]: L = [20.e-6, 200.e-6]

In [50]: apecosm.compute_spectra_ltl(ltl_zoo_mean, L, output_var='weight', label='Z00')
Out[50]: <matplotlib.lines.Line2D at 0x7f0f226e6680>

In [51]: L = [200.e-6, 2000.e-6]

In [52]: apecosm.compute_spectra_ltl(ltl_zoo2_mean, L, output_var='weight', label='Z002')
Out[52]: <matplotlib.lines.Line2D at 0x7f0f226e6860>

In [53]: L = [100e-6, 50000.e-6]

In [54]: apecosm.compute_spectra_ltl(ltl_goc_mean, L, output_var='weight', label='GOC')
Out[54]: <matplotlib.lines.Line2D at 0x7f0f22509b10>

In [55]: ax.set_xscale('log')

In [56]: ax.set_yscale('log')

In [57]: ax.set_ylim(1e-6, 1e18)
Out[57]: (1e-06, 1e+18)

In [58]: ax.set_ylabel("Biomass")
Out[58]: Text(0, 0.5, 'Biomass')

In [59]: ax.set_xlabel('Weight (kg)')
Out[59]: Text(0.5, 0, 'Weight (kg)')

In [60]: ax.set_title('All variables size-spectra')
Out[60]: Text(0.5, 1.0, 'All variables size-spectra')

In [61]: plt.legend()
Out[61]: <matplotlib.legend.Legend at 0x7f0f226ba590>
```


Fig. 4.11: Size-spectra of LTL and Apecosm variables as a function of weight

4.6 Weighted variable means

The computation of the horizontal average of a given variable V (functional response, growth rate or diet matrix), must be done by computed a weighted average, where the weight is provided by the biomass:

$$\overline{V(t, c, w)} = \frac{\sum_{x,y} V(t, x, y, c, w) \times OOPE(t, x, y, c, w) \times \Delta W(c, w) \times dS(x, y)}{\sum_{x,y} OOPE(t, x, y, c, w) \times \Delta W(c, w) \times dS(x, y)}$$

where V is the variable, $OOPE$ is the spatial OOPE, $\times dS(x, y)$ is the weight step and $dS(x, y)$ is the surface of the cell.

In the Apecosm package, this is achieved by using the `apecosm.extract_weighted_data()` function. For instance, to extract the mean functional response over the entire domain:

```
In [1]: mean_repfunct = apecosm.extract_weighted_data(data, const, mesh, 'repfonct_day')
```

```
In [2]: mean_repfunct
```

```
Out[2]:
```

```
<xarray.DataArray 'repfonct_day' (time: 12, c: 5, w: 100)>
dask.array<trudiv, shape=(12, 5, 100), dtype=float64, chunksize=(12, 5, 100),
↳ chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Coordinates:
  * time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
Dimensions without coordinates: c, w
```

Note that there is also the possibility to compute the mean over a given subregion as follows:

```
In [3]: regional_mean_repfunct = apecosm.extract_weighted_data(data,
...:                                                             const,
...:                                                             mesh,
...:                                                             'repfonct_day',
...:                                                             mask_dom=domain)
...:                                                             mask_dom=domain)
```

```
In [4]: regional_mean_repfunct
```

```
Out[4]:
```

```
<xarray.DataArray 'repfonct_day' (time: 12, c: 5, w: 100)>
dask.array<trudiv, shape=(12, 5, 100), dtype=float64, chunksize=(12, 5, 100),
↳ chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Coordinates:
  * time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
Dimensions without coordinates: c, w
```

It is now possible to plot the mean functional response as follows. First, we compute the time average:

```
In [5]: time_avg_mean_repfunct = apecosm.extract_time_means(mean_repfunct)
```

```
In [6]: time_avg_mean_repfunct
```

```
Out[6]:
```

```
<xarray.DataArray 'repfonct_day' (c: 5, w: 100)>
dask.array<mean_agg-aggregate, shape=(5, 100), dtype=float64, chunksize=(5, 100),
↳ chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Dimensions without coordinates: c, w
```

```

In [7]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))

In [8]: plt.subplots_adjust(hspace=0.4)

In [9]: for c in range(5):
...:     l = const['length'].isel(c=c)
...:     ax = plt.subplot(3, 2, c + 1)
...:     ax.plot(l, time_avg_mean_repfunct.isel(c=c))
...:     ax.set_xlim(const['length'].min(), const['length'].max())
...:     ax.set_ylim(0, 1)
...:     ax.grid(True)
...:     ax.set_xscale('log')
...:     ax.set_title('Repfonct, c = %d' %c)
...:

In [10]: plt.savefig(os.path.join('doc', 'computations', '_static', 'mean_repfonct.jpg'),
↳ bbox_inches='tight')

In [11]: plt.savefig(os.path.join('doc', 'computations', '_static', 'mean_repfonct.pdf'),
↳ bbox_inches='tight')

In [12]: plt.close(fig)

```


Fig. 4.12: Mean functional response

4.7 Diet calculation

If the diet outputs are available in the Apocosm simulations, it is possible to plot the diet matrix. This is achieved as follows.

First, the spatial mean diet is computed using the `apocosm.extract_weighted_data()` function.

```
In [1]: mean_diet = apocosm.extract_weighted_data(data, const, mesh, 'community_diet_
↳values')
```

```
In [2]: mean_diet
Out[2]:
<xarray.DataArray 'community_diet_values' (time: 12, c: 5, w: 100,
                                           prey_group: 11)>
dask.array<truediv, shape=(12, 5, 100, 11), dtype=float64, chunksize=(12, 5, 100, 11),
↳chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Coordinates:
  * time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
Dimensions without coordinates: c, w, prey_group
```

Then, the time average is computed using the `apocosm.extract_time_means()` function:

```
In [3]: time_average_mean_diet = apocosm.extract_time_means(mean_diet)
```

```
In [4]: time_average_mean_diet
Out[4]:
<xarray.DataArray 'community_diet_values' (c: 5, w: 100, prey_group: 11)>
array([[0.00000000e+00, 1.16958376e-02, 3.36429645e-01, ...,
        0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00],
       [0.00000000e+00, 6.58110429e-04, 2.05037589e-01, ...,
        0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00],
       [0.00000000e+00, 2.25934618e-05, 7.50818462e-02, ...,
        0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00],
       ...,
       [0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, ...,
        0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00],
       [0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, ...,
        0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00],
       [0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, ...,
        0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00]],
      ...
       [0.00000000e+00, 5.05430983e-03, 4.24286431e-01, ...,
        0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00],
       [0.00000000e+00, 3.64370196e-04, 2.88331625e-01, ...,
        0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00],
       [0.00000000e+00, 1.54795469e-05, 1.16834890e-01, ...,
        0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00],
      ...
       [0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, ...,
        1.23494882e-02, 4.50542931e-01, 4.68260016e-03],
       [0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, ...,
        9.17306606e-03, 4.57434365e-01, 4.20104523e-03],
       [0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, ...,
```

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```

6.88276820e-03, 4.64256169e-01, 2.82855885e-03]],
[[0.00000000e+00, 3.69589903e-03, 2.22155868e-01, ...,
 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00],
[0.00000000e+00, 9.97515701e-05, 1.20946352e-01, ...,
 8.21883233e-10, 8.80472859e-08, 1.01115388e-10],
[0.00000000e+00, 1.60166856e-06, 2.92084990e-02, ...,
 9.17596631e-07, 4.15164881e-05, 2.19734552e-08],
...,
[0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, ...,
 2.41670693e-02, 2.70518367e-01, 1.20115815e-01],
[0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, ...,
 2.43517255e-02, 2.64623213e-01, 1.25221374e-01],
[0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, ...,
 2.39167211e-02, 2.59136429e-01, 1.32259898e-01]]])
Dimensions without coordinates: c, w, prey_group

```

Now, the drawing of the diet matrix is done by using the `plot_diet_values()` function:

```

In [5]: fig = plt.figure()

In [6]: ax = plt.gca()

In [7]: l = apocosm.plot_diet_values(time_average_mean_diet, const, 0)

In [8]: plt.savefig(os.path.join('doc', 'computations', '_static', 'diet_com_0.jpg'),
↳ bbox_inches='tight')

In [9]: plt.savefig(os.path.join('doc', 'computations', '_static', 'diet_com_0.pdf'),
↳ bbox_inches='tight')

In [10]: plt.close(fig)

```

The first argument is the spatially and time averaged diet matrix, the second argument is the dataset containing all the Apecosm constants and the third argument is the community index.

Note that there is the possibility to control the legend layout by providing a `legend_args` argument, which is a dictionary containing the legend arguments.

Furthermore, the arguments of the Matplotlib `stackplot` function can also be included in the `apocosm.plot_diet_values()` function.

For instance:

```

In [11]: cmap = matplotlib.colormaps['jet']

In [12]: colors = [cmap(i / 10) for i in range(11)]

In [13]: fig = plt.figure()

In [14]: ax = plt.gca()

In [15]: l = apocosm.plot_diet_values(time_average_mean_diet, const, 0,
.....:                                 colors=colors, alpha=0.5,

```

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Fig. 4.13: Mean diet for community 0

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```

.....:         legend_args={'ncol': 2, 'fontsize': 6})
.....:
In [16]: plt.savefig(os.path.join('doc', 'computations', '_static', 'upt_diet_com_0.jpg
↳'), bbox_inches='tight')

In [17]: plt.savefig(os.path.join('doc', 'computations', '_static', 'upt_diet_com_0.pdf
↳'), bbox_inches='tight')

In [18]: plt.close(fig)

```


Fig. 4.14: Mean diet for community 0 with additional arguments for controlling the legend and stackplot display

To draw the diet matrix for all communities, a loop must be done over the c dimension:

```

In [19]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))

In [20]: plt.subplots_adjust(hspace=0.5)

In [21]: for c in range(5):
.....:     ax = plt.subplot(3, 2, c + 1)
.....:     draw_legend = (c == 0)
.....:     l = apcosm.plot_diet_values(time_average_mean_diet, const, c,
.....:                               colors=colors, alpha=0.5, draw_legend=draw_
↳legend,

```

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```

.....:                                     legend_args={'ncol': 3, 'fontsize': 6,
↳ 'framealpha': 0.5, 'loc': 'lower right'})
.....:     ax.set_xlabel('Length (m)')
.....:     ax.set_xlim(const['length'].min(), const['length'].max())
.....:
In [22]: plt.savefig(os.path.join('doc', 'computations', '_static', 'full_diet.jpg'),
↳ bbox_inches='tight')
In [23]: plt.savefig(os.path.join('doc', 'computations', '_static', 'full_diet.pdf'),
↳ bbox_inches='tight')
In [24]: plt.close(fig)

```


Fig. 4.15: Mean diet for all communities with additional arguments for controlling the legend and stackplot display

MAPPING

In the Apecosm package, we provide easy functions to draw Apecosm and NEMO/Pisces outputs on the original NEMO grid.

5.1 Quadmesh plots

The `apecosm.plot_pcolor_plot()` allows to easily draw 2D maps. For instance, in order to plot the total biomass, we first integrate over the full size-spectra, in order to get the biomass:

```
In [1]: biomass = apecosm.extract_oope_size_integration(data['OOPE'], const)

In [2]: biomass
Out[2]:
<xarray.DataArray (time: 12, y: 108, x: 163, c: 5)>
dask.array<sum-aggregate, shape=(12, 108, 163, 5), dtype=float64, chunksize=(12, 108, 163, 5), chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Coordinates:
  * time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
Dimensions without coordinates: y, x, c
```

Now, we sum the biomass over all the communities:

```
In [3]: tot_biomass = biomass.sum(dim='c')

In [4]: tot_biomass
Out[4]:
<xarray.DataArray (time: 12, y: 108, x: 163)>
array([[0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
       [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
       [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
       ...,
       [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
       [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
       [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.]],
      dtype=float64)

[[0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
 [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
 [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
 ...,
 [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.]]
```

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```

[0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
[0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.]],

[[0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
 [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
 [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
 ...,
 ...,
 [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
 [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
 [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.]],

[[0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
 [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
 [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
 ...,
 [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
 [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
 [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.]],

[[0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
 [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
 [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
 ...,
 [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
 [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
 [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.]]])
Coordinates:
  * time      (time) object 2018-01-16 00:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 00:00:00
Dimensions without coordinates: y, x

```

Then, we compute the time-average as follows:

```

In [5]: tavg_tot_biomass = apecosm.extract_time_means(tot_biomass)

In [6]: tavg_tot_biomass
Out[6]:
<xarray.DataArray (y: 108, x: 163)>
array([[0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
       [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
       [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
       ...,
       [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
       [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.],
       [0., 0., 0., ..., 0., 0., 0.]])
Dimensions without coordinates: y, x

```

Now that we have a DataArray with dimensions x and y, we can call the `apecosm.plot_pcolor_plot()` function:

```

In [7]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))

```

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```
In [8]: cs = apecosm.plot_pcolor_map(tavg_tot_biomass, mesh)
```

```
In [9]: cb = plt.colorbar(cs)
```

```
In [10]: cb.set_label('Biomass density (J/m2)')
```


Fig. 5.1: Example of a pcolor map drawn with the Apecosm package.

Note that in this example, the map is not projected. Therefore, X and Y axis show the cell indexes, not the real coordinates. In order to draw the outputs on a projected map, a projected axes must first be initialized, as follows:

```
In [11]: import cartopy.crs as ccrs
```

```
In [12]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
```

```
In [13]: ax = plt.axes(projection=ccrs.PlateCarree(central_longitude=180))
```

```
In [14]: cs = apecosm.plot_pcolor_map(tavg_tot_biomass, mesh, draw_land=True)
```

```
In [15]: cb = plt.colorbar(cs, shrink=0.5, location='bottom')
```

```
In [16]: cb.set_label('Biomass density (J/m2)')
```

The function will automatically detect that the current axes is a Geoaxes object. Consequently, it will manage the mapping. Note that the `plot_pcolor_map()` function can take all the arguments of the `pcolormesh` function. For

Fig. 5.2: Example of a **projected** pcolor map drawn with the Apecosm package.

instance, the colormap normalization can be changed.

To plot the biomass in log scale, we can first extract the minimum and maximum value to plot:

```
In [17]: import matplotlib.colors as color
In [18]: temp = tavg_tot_biomass.values
In [19]: temp = np.ma.masked_where((temp == 0), temp)
In [20]: vmin = temp.min()
In [21]: vmax = temp.max()
In [22]: vmin, vmax
Out[22]: (702.6092874353068, 153162.4179598088)
```

Then, we can define the log normalization of the colormap as follows:

```
In [23]: norm = color.LogNorm(vmin=vmin, vmax=vmax)
In [24]: norm
Out[24]: <matplotlib.colors.LogNorm at 0x7f0f23d90a90>
```

Finally, we can plot the map as follows:

```
In [25]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
```

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```
In [26]: ax = plt.axes(projection=ccrs.PlateCarree(central_longitude=180))
In [27]: cs = apecosm.plot_pcolor_map(tavg_tot_biomass, mesh, draw_land=True, norm=True, cmap='jet')
In [28]: cb = plt.colorbar(cs, shrink=0.5, location='bottom')
In [29]: cb.set_label('Biomass density (J/m2)')
```


Fig. 5.3: Example of a **projected** pcolor map drawn with the Apecosm package, with modified colormap and normalization

5.2 Contour plots

The `apecosm.plot_contour_plot()` allows to easily draw 2D contour maps. Using the same array as plotted in Section 5.1, the contour plot can be achieved as follows:

```
In [1]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
In [2]: cl = apecosm.plot_contour_map(tavg_tot_biomass, mesh)
In [3]: cb = plt.colorbar(cl)
In [4]: cb.set_label('Biomass density (J/m2)')
```


Fig. 5.4: Example of a contour plot map drawn with the Apecosm package.

In order to use filled contours, set the filled to True:

```
In [5]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
In [6]: cl = apecosm.plot_contour_map(tavg_tot_biomass, mesh, filled=True)
In [7]: cb = plt.colorbar(cl)
In [8]: cb.set_label('Biomass density (J/m2)')
```


Fig. 5.5: Example of a filled contour plot map drawn with the Apecosm package.

Note that the `apecosm.plot_contour_map()` can take all the parameters of the Matplotlib contour and contourf functions. For instance, to control the widths, colors and levels of the contour plots:

```
In [9]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
In [10]: cl = apecosm.plot_contour_map(tavg_tot_biomass, mesh, filled=False, draw_
↳ land=False,
.....:                               levels=21, colors='k', linewidths=2)
.....:
In [11]: cb = plt.colorbar(cl, orientation='horizontal')
In [12]: cb.set_label('Biomass density (J/m2)')
```


Fig. 5.6: Example of a contour plot map drawn with the Apecosm package, with the control of the contour parameters.

Note that in these examples, the map is not projected. Therefore, X and Y axis show the cell indexes, not the real coordinates.

In order to draw the outputs on a projected map, a projected axes must first be initialized, as follows:

```
In [13]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
In [14]: ax = plt.axes(projection=ccrs.PlateCarree(central_longitude=180))
In [15]: cl = apecosm.plot_contour_map(tavg_tot_biomass, mesh, filled=True, draw_
↪land=True)
In [16]: cb = plt.colorbar(cl, orientation='horizontal')
In [17]: cb.set_label('Biomass density (J/m2)')
```


Fig. 5.7: Example of a projected filled contour plot map drawn with the Apecosm package.

5.3 Combined

There is the possibility to combine both quadmesh and contour plots. For instance, if we want to superimpose the sea-surface temperature on top of the biomass, plotted in a log-scale, we first extract time-average sea-surface temperature:

```
In [1]: sst = ltl_data['thetao'].isel(z=0)

In [2]: sst
Out[2]:
<xarray.DataArray 'thetao' (time_counter: 12, y: 108, x: 163)>
dask.array<getitem, shape=(12, 108, 163), dtype=float32, chunksize=(12, 108, 163),
↳ chunktype=numpy.ndarray>
Coordinates:
  nav_lat      (y, x) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(108, 163), meta=np.ndarray>
  nav_lon      (y, x) float32 dask.array<chunksize=(108, 163), meta=np.ndarray>
  z            float32 0.5058
  time_centered (time_counter) object dask.array<chunksize=(12,), meta=np.ndarray>
  * time_counter (time_counter) object 2018-01-16 12:00:00 ... 2018-12-16 1...
Dimensions without coordinates: y, x
Attributes:
  standard_name:      sea_water_conservative_temperature
  long_name:          sea_water_potential_temperature
  units:              degree_C
  online_operation:   average
  interval_operation: 1 month
```

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```
interval_write:    1 month
cell_methods:     time: mean
cell_measures:    area: area
```

```
In [3]: sst_mean = apecosm.extract_time_means(sst)
```

```
In [4]: sst_mean
```

```
Out[4]:
```

```
<xarray.DataArray 'thetao' (y: 108, x: 163)>
array([[nan, nan, nan, ..., nan, nan, nan],
       [nan, nan, nan, ..., nan, nan, nan],
       [nan, nan, nan, ..., nan, nan, nan],
       ...,
       [nan, nan, nan, ..., nan, nan, nan],
       [nan, nan, nan, ..., nan, nan, nan],
       [nan, nan, nan, ..., nan, nan, nan]], dtype=float32)
Coordinates:
  nav_lat  (y, x) float32 -17.72 -17.72 -17.72 -17.72 ... 49.55 49.62 49.69
  nav_lon  (y, x) float32 132.5 133.5 134.5 135.5 ... -68.54 -67.54 -66.54
  z        float32 0.5058
Dimensions without coordinates: y, x
```

Now we prepare the quadmesh plot of biomass, as done in [Section 5.1](#):

```
In [5]: import matplotlib.colors as color
```

```
In [6]: temp = tavg_tot_biomass.values
```

```
In [7]: temp = np.ma.masked_where((temp == 0), temp)
```

```
In [8]: vmin = temp.min()
```

```
In [9]: vmax = temp.max()
```

```
In [10]: norm = color.LogNorm(vmin=vmin, vmax=vmax)
```

```
In [11]: norm
```

```
Out[11]: <matplotlib.colors.LogNorm at 0x7f0f28054d00>
```

```
In [12]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
```

```
In [13]: ax = plt.axes(projection=ccrs.PlateCarree(central_longitude=180))
```

```
In [14]: cs = apecosm.plot_pcolor_map(tavg_tot_biomass, mesh, draw_land=True, norm=norm,
↳ cmap='jet')
```

```
In [15]: cb = plt.colorbar(cs, shrink=0.5, location='bottom')
```

```
In [16]: cb.set_label('Biomass density (J/m2)')
```

```
In [17]: cl = apecosm.plot_contour_map(sst_mean, mesh, filled=False, draw_land=False,
.....:                                levels=21, colors='k', linewidths=1)
```

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.....

```
In [18]: plt.clabel(cl)
```

```
Out[18]: <a list of 28 text.Text objects>
```


Fig. 5.8: Example of a projected map of SST contours and biomass quadmesh plot

EXAMPLES

Here are provided some examples.

6.1 Extracting Nino 3.4 biomass

In this example, we show how to plot the time-series of total biomass over the Nino 3.4 area.

```
[1]: import os
import apecosm
import cartopy.crs as ccrs
import cartopy.feature as cfeature
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

```
[2]: mesh_file = os.path.join '..', 'data', 'pacific_mesh_mask.nc')
```

```
[3]: mesh = apecosm.open_mesh_mask(mesh_file)
```

```
[4]: dirin = os.path.join '..', 'data', 'apecosm')
```

```
[5]: const = apecosm.open_constants(dirin)
```

```
[6]: data = apecosm.open_apecosm_data(dirin, replace_dims={'community': 'c'})
```

Now, we extract the Nino 3.4 area, as described in <https://climatedataguide.ucar.edu/climate-data/nino-sst-indices-nino-12-3-34-4-oni-and-tni>

```
[7]: lon = mesh['glamt']
```

```
[8]: lat = mesh['gphit']
```

```
[9]: tmask = mesh['tmaskutil']
```

```
[10]: nino_mask = (abs(lat) <= 5) & (lon <= -120) & (lon >= -170) & (tmask > 0)
nino_mask = nino_mask.astype(int)
```

Now let's check that the area is properly set:

```
[11]: ax = plt.axes(projection=ccrs.PlateCarree(central_longitude=180))
cs = apecosm.plot_pcolor_map(nino_mask, mesh)
cb = plt.colorbar(cs, shrink=0.5)
```


Now we extract the spatial **mean** biomass density (in $J.kg^{-1}.m^{-2}$) over the area:

```
[12]: oope_nino_34 = apecosm.extract_oope_data(data['OOPE'], mesh, mask_dom=nino_mask)
oope_nino_34 = oope_nino_34.compute()
```

We convert the spatial mean into a spatial **integral** (in $J.kg^{-1}$)

```
[13]: oope_nino_34 = apecosm.spatial_mean_to_integral(oope_nino_34)
```

Now we integrate over the full size-spectrum:

```
[14]: biomass_nino_34 = apecosm.extract_oope_size_integriation(oope_nino_34, const)
```

Finally, we sum over the community (c) dimension to extract the total biomass over the Nino 3.4 area:

```
[15]: total_biomass_nino_34 = biomass_nino_34.sum(dim='c')
```

Now we can draw the time-series as follows:

```
[16]: ax = plt.gca()
total_biomass_nino_34.plot()
ax.set_title('Total biomass in Nino 34')
label = ax.set_ylabel('Biomass (J)')
```


6.2 Plotting mean functional response maps

In this example, we show how to plot the maps of mean functional response for small sizes (0 to 3cm)

Note that the `apecosm.extract_weighted_data` function cannot be used here, since the latter computes weighted **horizontal averages** of variables such as the functional response, and therefore produces time-series rather than maps

```
[1]: import os
import apecosm
import cartopy.crs as ccrs
import cartopy.feature as cfeature
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from mpl_toolkits.axes_grid1 import AxesGrid
from cartopy.mpl.geoaxes import GeoAxes

[2]: mesh_file = os.path.join '..', 'data', 'pacific_mesh_mask.nc')

[3]: mesh = apecosm.open_mesh_mask(mesh_file)

[4]: dirin = os.path.join '..', 'data', 'apecosm')
```

```
[5]: const = apecosm.open_constants(dirin)
```

```
[6]: data = apecosm.open_apecosm_data(dirin, replace_dims={'community': 'c'})
```

Now, we extract the biomass density and convert it using the `weight_step` variable, in order to obtain values in $J.m^{-2}$

```
[7]: oope = (data['OOPE'] * const['weight_step'])
```

Now we keep the `oope` variable where the length is greater than 3cm. OOPE for greater sizes is set to 0

```
[8]: oope_small = oope.where(const['length'] * 100 <= 3)
      oope_small = oope_small.fillna(0)
```

Now we weight the functional response using the `oope` variable and we average over all dimensions but `x`, `y` and `c`.

```
[9]: repfunct = data['repfonct_day'].weighted(oope_small)
      repfunct = repfunct.mean(dim=['time', 'w'])
      repfunct = repfunct.compute()
```

The result is 5 maps, one for each community, showing the mean functional response for each community.

```
[10]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))

      gridparams = {'crs': ccrs.PlateCarree(central_longitude=0), 'draw_labels':True,
                    'linewidth':0.5, 'color':'gray', 'alpha':0.5, 'linestyle':'--'}

      plt.rcParams['image.cmap'] = 'RdBu_r'

      for c in range(5):
          ax = plt.subplot(3, 2, c + 1, projection=ccrs.PlateCarree(central_longitude=180))
          cs = apecosm.plot_pcolor_map(repfunct.isel(c=c), mesh, axis=ax)
          cl = apecosm.plot_contour_map(repfunct.isel(c=c), mesh, axis=ax, filled=False,
          ↪ levels=[0.3], colors='red')
          cs.set_clim(0, 0.6)
          cb = plt.colorbar(cs, shrink=0.6)
          cb.set_label('Functional response')
          cb.set_ticks([0, 0.3, 0.6])
          cb.add_lines(cl)
          ax.set_title(f'Community {c + 1}')
          gl = ax.gridlines(**gridparams)
          gl.top_labels = False
          gl.right_labels = False
```


6.3 Plotting mean length maps

In this example, we show how to plot the maps of mean length

Note that the `apecosm.extract_weighted_data` function cannot be used here, since the latter computes weighted **horizontal averages** of variables such as the functional response, and therefore produces time-series rather than maps

```
[1]: import os
import apecosm
import cartopy.crs as ccrs
import cartopy.feature as cfeature
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from mpl_toolkits.axes_grid1 import AxesGrid
from cartopy.mpl.geoaxes import GeoAxes

[2]: mesh_file = os.path.join '..', 'data', 'pacific_mesh_mask.nc')

[3]: mesh = apecosm.open_mesh_mask(mesh_file)

[4]: dirin = os.path.join '..', 'data', 'apecosm')

[5]: const = apecosm.open_constants(dirin)
```

```
[6]: data = apecosm.open_apecosm_data(dirin, replace_dims={'community': 'c'})
```

Now, we extract the biomass density and convert it using the `weight_step` variable, in order to obtain values in $J.m^{-2}$. We also set the nan values to 0

```
[7]: oope = (data['OOPE'] * const['weight_step'])
      oope = oope.fillna(0)
```

Now we weight the length, in cm, using the `oope` variable and we average over all dimensions but `x`, `y` and `c`.

```
[10]: length = (const['length'] * 100).weighted(oope)
       length = length.mean(dim=['time', 'w'])
       length = length.compute()
```

The result is 5 maps, one for each community, showing the mean length for each community.

```
[11]: fig = plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))

      gridparams = {'crs': ccrs.PlateCarree(central_longitude=0), 'draw_labels':True,
                   'linewidth':0.5, 'color':'gray', 'alpha':0.5, 'linestyle':'--'}

      plt.rcParams['image.cmap'] = 'RdBu_r'

      for c in range(5):
          ax = plt.subplot(3, 2, c + 1, projection=ccrs.PlateCarree(central_longitude=180))
          cs = apecosm.plot_pcolor_map(length.isel(c=c), mesh, axis=ax)
          cs.set_clim(length.isel(c=c).min(), length.isel(c=c).max())
          cb = plt.colorbar(cs, shrink=0.6)
          cb.set_label('Mean length (cm)')
          ax.set_title(f'Community {c + 1}')
          gl = ax.gridlines(**gridparams)
          gl.top_labels = False
          gl.right_labels = False
```


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7.1 Reading configuration

<code>read_config(filename[, relative_to_main, ...])</code>	Reads configuration files.
---	----------------------------

7.1.1 apecosm.read_config

`apecosm.read_config(filename, relative_to_main=False, params=None, path="")`

Reads configuration files.

Parameters

- **filename** (*str*) – The main configuration file.
- **relative_to_main** (*bool, optional*) – True if path names are related to the main configuration file, False if path names are related to the current configuration file.
- **params** (*dict, optional*) – Dictionary that contains all the parameters.
- **path** (*str, optional*) – Path that is used to reconstruct the sub-configuration file names.

Returns

A dictionary containing all the parameters.

Return type

dict

7.2 Reading grid

<code>extract_weight_grid(config)</code>	Extracts weight grid attributes.
<code>read_ape_grid(filename)</code>	Reads the Apecosm text file containing depth coordinates of Apecosm T-grid points.
<code>partial_step_ape(ape_grid, mesh_file_nemo)</code>	Reads the NEMO mesh file to extract the Apecosm vertical grid
<code>plot_grid_nemo_ape(ape_grid, mesh_file_nemo, ...)</code>	Draws the NEMO and Apecosm vertical grid at points <i>ilat, ilon</i> .

7.2.1 `apecosm.extract_weight_grid`

`apecosm.extract_weight_grid(config)`

Extracts weight grid attributes. Returns the weight and length step used for integration

7.2.2 `apecosm.read_ape_grid`

`apecosm.read_ape_grid(filename)`

Reads the Apecosm text file containing depth coordinates of Apecosm T-grid points.

Parameters

filename (*str*) – Apecosm vertical grid file

Returns

A tuple containing the depth and thicknesses of the cell points

Todo: Add correction: in the new version, the `.txt` file provides the lower edge of the T grid

7.2.3 `apecosm.partial_step_ape`

`apecosm.partial_step_ape(ape_grid, mesh_file_nemo)`

Reads the NEMO mesh file to extract the Apecosm vertical grid

Parameters

- **ape_grid** – CSV file containing the Apecosm vertical levels
- **mesh_file_nemo** – NetCDF file containing the NEMO mesh file

7.2.4 `apecosm.plot_grid_nemo_ape`

`apecosm.plot_grid_nemo_ape(ape_grid, mesh_file_nemo, ilat, ilon)`

Draws the NEMO and Apecosm vertical grid at points *ilat*, *ilon*.

7.3 Data extraction

<code>open_mesh_mask(mesh_file[, replace_dims])</code>	Opens a NEMO mesh mask.
<code>open_ltl_data(dirin[, replace_dims])</code>	Opens NEMO/PISCES outputs.
<code>open_constants(dirin[, replace_dims])</code>	Opens an Apecosm constant file.
<code>open_apecosm_data(dirin[, replace_dims])</code>	Opens Apecosm outputs.
<code>extract_ltl_data(data_array, mesh[, ...])</code>	Extraction of LTL values on a given domain.
<code>extract_time_means(data[, time])</code>	Extract data time mean.
<code>extract_oope_data(data, mesh[, mask_dom])</code>	Extraction of OOPE values on a given domain.
<code>generate_mask(mesh, domain)</code>	Function that generates a mask, with ones where the points are in a given area, 0 elsewhere.
<code>spatial_mean_to_integral(data)</code>	Converts a spatial mean into an integral by multiplying by the total surface
<code>extract_mean_size(...)</code>	Extracts the mean length or weight.
<code>extract_weighted_data(data, const, mesh, var-name)</code>	Extracts data outputs and weight them using biomass outputs.

7.3.1 apecosm.open_mesh_mask

`apecosm.open_mesh_mask(mesh_file, replace_dims=None)`

Opens a NEMO mesh mask. It removes the *t* dimension from the dataset.

Parameters

- **mesh_file** (*str*) – Full path of the mesh file.
- **replace_dims** (*dict*, *optional*) – Dictionary that is used to rename dimension names by other names

Returns

A dataset containing the variables of the mesh mask.

Return type

`xarray.Dataset`

7.3.2 apecosm.open_ltl_data

`apecosm.open_ltl_data(dirin, replace_dims=None, **kwargs)`

Opens NEMO/PISCES outputs.

Parameters

- **dirin** (*str*) – Input directory.
- **replace_dims** (*dict*, *optional*) – Dictionary that is used to rename dimensions

7.3.3 apecosm.open_constants

`apecosm.open_constants(dirin, replace_dims=None)`

Opens an Apecosm constant file. It will look for a file that contains *Constant*.

Parameters

- **dirin** (*str*) – Input directory.
- **replace_dims** (*dict*, *optional*) – Dictionary that is used to rename dimensions

7.3.4 apecosm.open_apecosm_data

`apecosm.open_apecosm_data(dirin, replace_dims=None, **kwargs)`

Opens Apecosm outputs.

Parameters

- **dirin** (*str*) – Input directory.
- **replace_dims** (*dict*, *optional*) – Dictionary that is used to rename dimensions

7.3.5 apecosm.extract_ltl_data

`apecosm.extract_ltl_data(data_array, mesh, mask_dom=None, depth_limits=(None, None))`

Extraction of LTL values on a given domain. LTL is vertically integrated and spatially averaged over the domain.

Parameters

- **data_array** – NEMO/Pisces dataset
- **mesh** (*xarray.Dataset*) – Mesh grid dataset
- **mask_dom** (*numpy.array*) – Mask array. If None, full domain is considered
- **depth_limits** (*int*) – Array with the two depths limits used for integration

Returns

A *xarray* dataset

7.3.6 apecosm.extract_time_means

`apecosm.extract_time_means(data, time=None)`

Extract data time mean.

Parameters

- **data** (*xarray.Dataset*) – Apecosm dataset
- **time** (*str*) – Time mean. Can be time average ('tot'), yearly means ('year'), seasonal means ('season') or monthly means ('monthly')

Returns

A data array with the given time mean

7.3.7 apecosm.extract_oope_data

`apecosm.extract_oope_data(data, mesh, mask_dom=None)`

Extraction of OOPE values on a given domain. OOPE is spatially integrated over the domain.

Parameters

- **data** (`xarray.Dataset`) – Apecosm dataset
- **mesh** (`xarray.Dataset`) – Mesh grid dataset
- **const** (`xarray.Dataset`) – Apecosm constants dataset
- **mask_dom** (`numpy.array`, optional) – Array containing the area mask
- **use_wstep** (`bool`, optional) – True if data must be multiplied by weight step (conversion from $J.m^{-2}.kg^{-1}$ to $J.m^{-2}$)

Returns

A tuple with the time-value and the LTL time series

7.3.8 apecosm.generate_mask

`apecosm.generate_mask(mesh, domain)`

Function that generates a mask, with ones where the points are in a given area, 0 elsewhere.

Parameters

- **mesh** (`class:xarray.Dataset`) – Dataset containing the grid definition.
- **domain** (`dict`, `str`) – Domain to extract. If string is provided, must be a predefined area. If a dict is provided, it must contain a *lon* and a *lat* key, containing the area coordinates.

7.3.9 apecosm.spatial_mean_to_integral

`apecosm.spatial_mean_to_integral(data)`

Converts a spatial mean into an integral by multiplying by the total surface

7.3.10 apecosm.extract_mean_size

`apecosm.extract_mean_size(spatially_integrated_biomass, const, varname)`

Extracts the mean length or weight.

Parameters

- **spatially_integrated_biomass** – Biomass integrated over a given region (dim: time, c, w). Must be in $J.kg^{-1}$
- **const** (`xarray.Dataset`) – Apecosm constants dataset
- **mesh** (`xarray.Dataset`) – Mesh grid dataset
- **varname** (`str`) – Name of the variable to extract (*length* or *weight*)
- **mask_dom** (`numpy.array`, optional) – Array of domain mask
- **aggregate** (`bool`, optional) – True if community is included in the mean. If False, output depends on community.

7.3.11 apecosm.extract_weighted_data

`apecosm.extract_weighted_data(data, const, mesh, varname, mask_dom=None, dims=('x', 'y'))`

Extracts data outputs and weight them using biomass outputs.

Parameters

- **data** (`xarray.Dataset`) – Apecosm dataset
- **const** (`xarray.Dataset`) – Apecosm constants dataset
- **mesh** (`xarray.Dataset`) – Mesh grid dataset
- **varname** (`str`) – Name of the variable to extract (`repfonct_day` for instance)
- **mask_dom** (`numpy.array`, optional) – Array of domain mask
- **dims** – Dimensions over which to perform the average.

7.4 Habitat

<code>get_tcor(temp_array[, ta, tref])</code>	Computes the Ahrrenius temperature as follows:
<code>compute_o2(oxy_array[, tcor, oxyresp, oxylim])</code>	Computes the oxygen habitat function:
<code>compute_tpref(tcor[, sigm_tcor])</code>	Computes the temperature preference function:
<code>compute_tlim(temp_array[, t_sup, t_inf, ...])</code>	Computes the temperature limitation function:
<code>compute_lightpref(par, daylen[, opt_light, ...])</code>	Computes the light preference function.

7.4.1 apecosm.get_tcor

`apecosm.get_tcor(temp_array, ta=5020.0, tref=298.15)`

Computes the Ahrrenius temperature as follows:

$$\exp \frac{T_a}{T_{ref}} - \frac{T_a}{T}$$

Parameters

temp_array (`numpy.array`) – Temperature (in *K*)

7.4.2 apecosm.compute_o2

`apecosm.compute_o2(oxy_array, tcor=1.0, oxyresp=100000.0, oxylim=0.0001)`

Computes the oxygen habitat function:

$$H_{oxy} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp [OXYRESP \times (T_{cor} \times OXYLIM - Oxy)]}$$

Parameters

- **oxy_array** (`numpy.array`) – Oxygen (in *mol.L⁻¹*)
- **tcor** (`numpy.array`) – Ahrrenius temperature (obtained from the `get_tcor()` function)

7.4.3 apecosm.compute_tpref

`apecosm.compute_tpref(tcors, sigm_tcors=0.1)`

Computes the temperature preference function:

$$H_{tpref} = \exp \left[-0.5 \left(\frac{\frac{T_{cor}(z)}{T_{cor}(z=0)} - 1}{SIGMTCOR} \right)^2 \right]$$

Parameters

tcors (*numpy.array*) – Arrhenius temperature (obtained from the `get_tcors()` function)

Danger: The temperature array should be 4D, with z as the second dimension.

7.4.4 apecosm.compute_tlim

`apecosm.compute_tlim(temp_array, t_sup=280.15, t_inf=268.5, ta_lim_sup=200000, ta_lim_inf=200000)`

Computes the temperature limitation function:

$$H_{tlim} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp \left(\frac{T_{aLIM}}{temp} - \frac{T_{aLIM}}{T_{inf}} \right)} \times \frac{1}{1 + \exp \left(\frac{T_{aLIM}}{T_{sup}} - \frac{T_{aLIM}}{temp} \right)}$$

7.4.5 apecosm.compute_lightpref

`apecosm.compute_lightpref(par, daylen, opt_light=100.0, sigm_light=170.0, same_daynight=False, nfact=1e-06)`

Computes the light preference function.

$$light = \frac{PAR}{DAYLENGTH} * nfactor + EPS$$

$$H_{lpref} = H_{lpred} = \frac{mode}{light} \times \exp \left[\frac{(\log(mode) - \mu)^2 - (\log(light) - \mu)^2}{2 \times \sigma} \right]$$

Parameters

- **par** (*numpy.array*) – Photosynthetically Active Radiation (in $W.m^{-2}$). **Should be 4D (time, z, y, x).**
- **daylen** (*numpy.array*) – Fraction of day within 24h (can be obtained from the `compute_daylength()` function). Its shape should allow broadcasting with the par array (for instance, if par=(time, depth, y, x), daylen should be (time, 1, y, x). Should correspond with the time step of the PAR files.
- **same_daynight** (*bool*) – Whether light habitat should distinguish day and night cycles.
- **nfactor** (*float*) – Proportionality coefficient between light intensity at night and during the day.

Returns

An array of dimensions (dn, time, z, y, x), with dn=0 for daytime, dn=1 for night time.

Note: This function can also be used to compute the light contribution to the functional response.

7.5 Miscellaneous

<code>size_to_weight(size)</code>	Converts size (in m) into weight (in kg) #
<code>weight_to_size(weight)</code>	Converts weight (in kg) into size (in m)
<code>find_percentile(data[, percentage])</code>	Extract percentile to saturate the colormaps.
<code>compute_daylength(lat[, nlon])</code>	Computes the day-length fraction providing a latitude array by using the same formulation as in APECOSM.
<code>extract_community_names(const)</code>	Extracts community names from the units attribute in the OOPE NetCDF file.

7.5.1 `apecosm.size_to_weight`

`apecosm.size_to_weight(size)`

Converts size (in m) into weight (in kg) #

$$W = AL^3$$

7.5.2 `apecosm.weight_to_size`

`apecosm.weight_to_size(weight)`

Converts weight (in kg) into size (in m)

..math:

$$L = \left(\frac{W}{A}\right)^{\{-3\}}$$

7.5.3 `apecosm.find_percentile`

`apecosm.find_percentile(data, percentage=1)`

Extract percentile to saturate the colormaps. They are computed from unmasked arrays

Parameters

- **data** (`numpy.array`) – Data array
- **percentage** – Percentage used to saturate the colormap.

Returns

A tuple containing the lower and upper bounds (`cmin`, `cmax`)

7.5.4 apecosm.compute_daylength

`apecosm.compute_daylength(lat, nlon=None)`

Computes the day-length fraction providing a latitude array by using the same formulation as in APECOSM.

Parameters

- **lat** (`numpy.array`) – Latitude array (either 1D or 2D)
- **nlon** (`int`, *optional*) – Number of longitudes

Returns

A 2D array with the daylength fraction

7.5.5 apecosm.extract_community_names

`apecosm.extract_community_names(const)`

Extracts community names from the units attribute in the OOPE NetCDF file. It uses regular expressions to extract the names. *community* must be a variable in the NetCDF variable.

Parameters

data (`xarray.Dataset`) – xarray dataset that is returned when using `xr.open_dataset` on the output file.

Returns

The list of community names

7.6 Maps

Warning: The following functions need the PyNgl library. This could be done by setting up a virtual environment.

For more details, please visit <https://www.pyngl.ucar.edu/Download/>

<code>plot_pcolor_map(data, mesh[, axis, draw_land])</code>	Draws 2D OOPE maps.
<code>plot_contour_map(data, mesh[, filled, axis, ...])</code>	Draws 2D OOPE maps.

7.6.1 apecosm.plot_pcolor_map

`apecosm.plot_pcolor_map(data, mesh, axis=None, draw_land=True, **kwargs)`

Draws 2D OOPE maps.

Parameters

- **data** (`xarray.DataArray`) – Data to plot
- **mesh** (`xarray.Dataset`) – Mesh dataset
- **ax** (`matplotlib.axes._subplots.AxesSubplot` or `cartopy.mpl.geoaxes.GeoAxesSubplot`, *optional*) – Axis on which to draw
- ****kwargs** – Additional arguments to the *pcolormesh* function

Returns

The output quad mesh.

Return type

`matplotlib.collections.QuadMesh`

7.6.2 `apecosm.plot_contour_map`

`apecosm.plot_contour_map(data, mesh, filled=False, axis=None, draw_land=False, **kwargs)`

Draws 2D OOPE maps.

Parameters

- **data** (`xarray.DataArray`) – Data to plot
- **mesh** (`xarray.Dataset`) – Mesh dataset
- **ax** (`matplotlib.axes._subplots.AxesSubplot` or `cartopy.mpl.geoaxes.GeoAxesSubplot`, optional) – Axis on which to draw
- ****kwargs** – Additional arguments to the `pcolormesh` function

Returns

The output quad mesh.

Return type

`matplotlib.collections.QuadMesh`

7.7 Size spectra

<code>compute_spectra_ltl(data, L[, N, conv, ...])</code>	Computes the size/weight spectra for lower trophic levels (i.e. PISCES variables).
<code>plot_oope_spectra(data, const[, output_var])</code>	Plots the OOPE size spectra.

7.7.1 `apecosm.compute_spectra_ltl`

`apecosm.compute_spectra_ltl(data, L, N=100, conv=0.001, output_var='weight', **kwargs)`

Computes the size/weight spectra for lower trophic levels (i.e. PISCES variables).

Weight spectra:

$$P(w) = aw^{-1}$$

$$PHY2 = a \int_{w_1}^{w_2} w^{-1} dw = a \ln \left(\frac{w_2}{w_1} \right)$$

$$a = \frac{PHY2}{\ln \left(\frac{w_2}{w_1} \right)}$$

Length spectra:

$$P(l) = bl^{-1}$$

$$PHY2 = b \int_{l_1}^{l_2} l^{-1} dl = a \ln \left(\frac{l_2}{l_1} \right)$$

$$b = \frac{PHY2}{\ln \left(\frac{l_2}{l_1} \right)}$$

Parameters

- **data** (*numpy.array / float*) – LTL content (number of moles), either a float or a 1D array
- **L** (*list*) – Size limits of the LTL class
- **N** (*int*) – Number of weight class to draw.
- **conv** (*float*) – Conversion factor to move from LTL units to mol/m3 (Apecosm units)
- **out** (*str*) – ‘weight’ if weight spectra should be drawn, else ‘length’ for a size spectra

Returns

A tuple containing the weight, length array and the corresponding biomass

7.7.2 apecosm.plot_oope_spectra

`apecosm.plot_oope_spectra(data, const, output_var='weight', **kwargs)`

Plots the OOPE size spectra. Since OOPE data are stored in $J.m^{-3}.kg^{-1}$, they must be converted into $J.m^{-3}.m^{-1}$:

$$a \int_{w_i}^{w_{i+1}} w^{-1} dw = b \int_{l_i}^{l_{i+1}} l^{-3} dl$$

$$\xi(w_i) \delta w_i = \xi(l_i) \delta l_i$$

$$\xi(l_i) = \xi(w_i) \frac{\delta w_i}{\delta l_i}$$

Parameters

- **data** (*xarray.Dataset*) – A OOPE dataset that must be 2-dimensional (community, weight)
- **output_var** (*str*) – ‘length’ if size spectra should be plotted, else weight spectra is plotted.

return None

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